

WOMEN ENTREPRENEUR: Issues and Challenges of Women entrepreneurs in India

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Abstract

In twenty first Century, the transformation of social material of the Indian society, in terms of magnified academic standing of girls and varied aspirations for higher living, necessitated a modification in the life style of Indian women. Social and economic development of girls is important for overall economic development of any society or a rustic. Entrepreneurship is that the state of mind that many ladies have in her however has not been capitalized in India in approach during which it ought to be. Due to modification in atmosphere, currently individuals are more leisurely to just accept leading role of girls in our society, though there are some exceptions. She has competed with man and with success stood up with him in each walk of life and business. These ladies' leaders are assertive, persuasive and willing to require risks. They managed to survive and succeed in this cut throat competition with their hard work, diligence and perseverance. Developing and developed nations have realised that developing lady's entrepreneurship is indispensable to flourish, as economically dominant nations within the trendy sophisticated world. Therefore, creation of platforms and networks for entrepreneurial culture are outstanding problems globally. In these circumstances the difficulties long-faced by ladies' bourgeois and their standing within the society are mentioned.

Keywords: Women Entrepreneurs, capitalized, transformation, creation of platform, obstacles, global perspective, Opportunities.

Introduction:

"The best measuring device to the progress of a nation is its treatment of its ladies." **Swami Vivekananda**

Within the twenty first century the business ladies within the kind of lady's entrepreneurs are highest rising entrepreneurial populations within the India. In this gift era, the well-read women do not want to bind their lives in the four walls of the houses. A woman is jam-packed with life as she plays several roles in her life. A woman may be a pilot of a family and successively nation. They can demand for equal respect from others. However, there's a protracted approach for Indian ladies to attain equal rights and position as a result of our Indian Society traditions are deep frozen and our society remains currently male dominated one. In spite of all social barriers, Indian women try to achieve their target. They manage to endure in this cut throat competition with their hard work. The current development and changes in the world show that women are currently making notable contribution towards the wealth of the country. Forbes reports that they are becoming more entrepreneurial, owning more than 36% of all businesses in 2012 [35]. This was a tremendous jump from year 2007. The Global Entrepreneurship Monitor (GEM) reported that there are 126 million women starting or running businesses. Among them 98 million operating established (over three and a half years) businesses. That's how women entrepreneurs are impacting the global economy.

Methodology Of Study

This is a conceptual paper and the researcher has adopted the method of reviewing different research

articles, research journals, websites, eBooks and case studies, to collect data about entrepreneurship and woman entrepreneurship which is consequently incorporated as an inspiration paper written by the investigator. The study relies on secondary sources of knowledge. The main objective of the study is to know and to study of current scenario of women entrepreneur, and also to study of the obstacles faced by women entrepreneur. The researchers have placed their own observations relating to identical.

Literature Review

The focus of literature review will be at the concept of entrepreneurship, and then drive on to look at female entrepreneurship and related definitions. An important tool thought about in permitting feminine management and liberation is feminine Entrepreneurship. Directing a literature review may be an important component of the analysis method. This paper appearance at the literature around feminine entrepreneurs, concentrating on feminine entrepreneurship in India. Vosle in 1994 quoted that "The bourgeois is one UN agency drives the method of economic process and mediates the inputs and outputs of the economic system". Singh and Belwal (2008: 1) Quote Desai (1999) to explain the roots of the word bourgeois. They state "The word bourgeois springs from the French verb enterprendre . meaning to undertake". "Schumpeter (1934) represented the bourgeois because the originator UN agency introduces one thing new into Associate in Nursing economy" Kirzner (1997-authors own addition) stressed the fact that the entrepreneur is the decision maker in a particular cultural context, who

commands a range of behaviour's that exploit these opportunities".

Women Entrepreneurs In Current Scenario

This is the century of telecommunication, IT and financial institutions. Women's experience all told these industries is starting to emerge and ladies are rising as a force to reckon with. Many of those new industries are headed and guided by ladies UN agency are seen as pioneers and mavericks. The loci of power have shifted away from traditional venues such as old boys clubs, golf courses and cigar smoking rooms to power now being vested with energetic new upstarts figuring out of their homes or on their laptop terminals from home. This new pot of chance will become the proverbial melting pot for professionally trained and enterprising ladies. Here there are fewer barriers to overcome, less pre-conceived notions, fewer well entrenched assumptions and rules and lesser gender agenda in the secondary environment. The transition to consecutive millennium is wherever the ladies can produce new paradigms of being a female offspring UN agency takes the responsibility of her folks, is a wife who wishes to create a home and a family, a mother who takes a charge of the children to make them the children of the new millennium. She is additionally the bourgeois UN agency builds Associate in Nursing enterprise and discovers her relevancy and that means of her life in herself. She accepts the individuality of her identity and is willing to share the house. Simultaneously with all the dreams of intimacy she searches for mutuality, dignity and respect. She is additionally hospitable a life while not wedding and a parenting while not a father. Women of nowadays have a brand-new avatar within the free rolling 90's.

Top Most Women Entrepreneurs In India

Successful Women Entrepreneurs in India of 21st Century

1. Divya Gokulnath, CoFounder , BYJU'S
2. Falguni Nayar ,Founder and CEO, NYKAA
3. Ekta Kapoor, Creative Director, balaji Telefilms Ltd
4. Swati Paradkar, President, Lijjat Papad.
5. Kiran Mazumdar Shaw, Chairman & Managing director, Biocon Ltd.
6. Sabina Chopra, Co-Founder, Yatra.Com
7. Swati Piramal, Vice Chairperson, Piramal Enterprises Ltd.
8. Preetha Reddy, Managing Director, Apollo hospitals.
9. Naina Lal Kidwai, CEO and Country Head (india) ,HSBC
10. Malvika Hegde CEO Of Café Coffee Day

Women Entrepreneurs

Women entrepreneurs may be defined as the women or group of women who commence and operate a

business venture. Such women are also known as women business owners or women entrepreneurs or self employed women. Women entrepreneur defined by government of India is 'an enterprise owned and controlled by women having a minimum financial interest of 51% of the capital and giving at least 51% of the employment generated in the enterprise to women' like male entrepreneurs a women entrepreneur ha many functions. They should study the prospects of starting new project, undertake risks introduction of new ideas. Communication of business and providing ingenious leadership in all aspects of business. Women entrepreneurs are effectively increasing in the economies of almost all countries. The hidden skills, potentials about business of women have been increasing with the growing sensitively of the role and economic status in the society. The knowledge skill and compliance in business are the come reasons for women to come forward in toe business enterprise. Women engaged in business due to pull and push factors which give confidence to women to have self sufficient occupation and stored on their foot. Due to entrepreneurship women become confidant independent decision-making power is increased. A strong desire to do enoronous positive is an integral quality of entrepreneurial women. Entrepreneur women complete contribute values in both family and social life due to different media women become conscious about their qualities, rights and also the work situations.

Woman Enterprises In Developed Countries

The growth issue is especially necessary in high financial gain countries wherever girls ar more and more getting into technology primarily based business ventures. As compared to males females-owned corporations show that companies headed by girls tend to be smaller & grow a lot of slowly than those headed by men. Generally, smaller in size & slower growth rates are perceived as issues. Shane and venkataraman, (2000). Indeed, girls face multi-dimensional challenges like external finance as business house owners & managers. Additional barriers include socialization networks & practices, family roles and possible lack of business contacts. Disadvantages practised by girls altogether these areas are widely believed to end in higher failure rates & lower growth rates for girls closely-held businesses. Bowen, and Hisrich, (1986). An increasing variety of students believe that the expansion of a business is a minimum of, partially determined by the entrepreneur's motivations.

Owned enterprises over the past sixteen years remains over the national average. As per stock market OPEN State of Women-Owned Business Report, the top-ranking countries on the basis of the revenue generation by the women-led firms are Ghana (No. 1-46.04%), Russia (No. 2-

34.06%), Uganda (No.3-33.08%), New Zealand(No.4-33.00%) and India (No.48- 11.00%) A sense towards sovereign deciding is that the key issue to settle on the profession as a challenge. Saddled with house chores Associate in Nursing different responsibilities towards her family women need to urge liberty underneath the influence of those factors and as an urge to try to one thing new. Such circumstances are known as pull factors. In case of push factors women engaged in business activities because of family pressure and therefore the responsibility is drive upon them.

Rank	Country	Women Business Owners (%)
1	Ghana	46.04%
2	Russia	34.06%
3	Uganda	33.08%
4	New Zealand	33.00%
48	India	11.00%

Women Entrepreneurship in India

Sr.No.	Name of the State	No.Of Units Registered	No.Of Women enterprises	Percentage
1	Tamil Nādu	9618	2930	30.36
2	Uttar Pradesh	7980	3180	39.84
3	Kerala	5487	2135	38.91
4	Punjab	4791	1618	33.71
5	Maharashtra	4339	1394	32.12
6	Gujrat	3872	1538	39.72
7	Karnataka	3822	1026	26.84
8	Madhya Pradesh	2967	842	28.38
9	Other States and UTS	14576	4185	28.71
Total		57452	18848	32.82

Source – World bank Report

Obstacles faced By Women Entrepreneurs in India:

In Indian context attitude towards the women are still conquered by the tough resistance from the male ego and the problem of Indian women pertains to her key responsibility towards family. From the beginning till the enterprise function, women entrepreneur comes across a series of problem. In rural areas women are considered as helpers. The main obstacles faced by women entrepreneurs are as follows:

1. The biggest turning point of a woman' life is marriage. She turned into a daughters-in-laws from a daughter. The priority is also changed with this. The dream of a woman has ripped like a fruit. Expectation from the family and personal commitment are mostly a great barrier for succeeding in business career. In such circumstances, it will be very much complicated to focus and run their enterprise successfully.

Sources – CEO World Magazine Present Position Of Women Entrepreneurs In India

Women represent close to 1/2 the entire world population yet as in Asian country conjointly. Women are the better half of the society. In our societies Indian girls at treated as show items to be unbroken reception. But currently they're conjointly enjoying the impact of globalisation not solely on domestic however conjointly on international sphere. Women take off of the four walls to contribute altogether activities. Indian girls at able to take burden of labour in house and yet because the work place. From several survey it's discovered that the feminine entrepreneurs from Asian country are manufacturing a lot of capitals than the opposite a part of the planet. Since middle 1991, a drastic change takes place in Indian Economy. India has great entrepreneurial potential. At the current era, girls' participation in monetary activities is marked by a coffee work participation rate. India provides a good example of entrepreneurs.

Because Indian women are much conscious about their family obligations compare to business responsibility.

2. Cast and religions dominator also hinder women entrepreneur. For this women entrepreneur cannot overcome the obstacle before them to grow and flourish. In rural areas, women face more social and political obstacle.
3. Though our constitution speaks of equality between sexes, male patriot is still the order of the day. Male dominated society destroys a female capability ability shows much less than male.
4. In our India 60% of total women are illiterate. They are far behind in the field of education. Due to lack of appropriate education, women entrepreneurs are in dark about the rapidly growing new technology, new methods of production, marketing techniques, and other governmental policy.

5. Different institutions in the financial sector expand their utmost support in the form of different incentives, loans etc. Many woman entrepreneurs do not aware of all these assistances provided by the institutions. Even the financial institutes are not coming forward to give financial assistance to. In the present market scenario, the competition is too high; women entrepreneurs must survive in the market against the male counterpart who has enormous experience and capacity to adopt technology in running enterprises.
6. For running an enterprise risk-bearing capacity is essential. But a woman in India by character is very shy. Beside this due to no adoption or slow adoption to changing technology also reduce their risk-taking ability.
7. For an enterprise a good management is necessary. But many of women entrepreneurs are not efficient at all in some managerial functions like planning, staffing, directing, controlling, motivating, and coordinating. Therefore, inadequate managerial ability of women becomes a problem for them to run the enterprise successfully.
8. Moving alone for business purposes are still seemed to be with suspicious eyes. Sometimes, younger women feel uncomfortable when dealing with men for work related aspects.
9. Since women cannot run here and there for promotion, supply and money collection, they have to depend upon the middle men for these activities. Middle men lean to exploit them in the excuse of helping. These result in less sales and lesser profit.
10. Self-motivation, self-confidence are the key ingredients for a successful business. But women suffer with lack of self-confidence because of their inborn nature.

Table 1: Govt Plan for the Growth of Women Entrepreneurship through Five Year

Sr.No	Five Year Plan	Year	Inspections of women
1	First Five-Year Plan	(1951-56)	Visualized a number of welfare measures for women. Sets up the central and social welfare board
2	Second Five-Year Plan	(1956-61)	Supported the development of women to work at the grass roots.
3	Third and Fourth FiveYear Plans	(1961-66 To 1969-74)	supported female education as a major welfare Measure
4	Fifth Five-Year Plan	(1974-79)	emphasized training of women
5	Sixth Five-Year Plan	(1980-85)	recognized women's lack of access to resources as a critical factor indpending their growth
6	Seventh Five-Year Plan	(1985-90)	emphasized the need for gender equality
7	Eight Five-Year Plan	(1992-97)	focused on empowering women, especially at the grass roots level
8	Ninth Five-Year Plan	(1997-2002)	adopted a strategy of women's component plan
9	Tenth Five-Year Plan	(2002-07)	aims at empowering women through translating the recently adopted National Policy for Empowerment
10	Eleventh Five Year Plan	(2007-2012)	encourage women in setting up their own venturesof Women (2001)
11	Twelve Five Year Plan	(2012-2017)	Faster sustainable and more inclusive growth

Right efforts are required in the improvement of women entrepreneurs and their greater contribution

in the entrepreneurial activities. Women entrepreneurs need to be given assurance, freedom,

and mobility to come out of their absurdities. The following actions are recommended to authorize the women to grab different opportunities and face challenges in their business.

Limitation And Future Directions

The study has several limitations. Firstly, while the study psychoanalyzes the relationship between women entrepreneur and family. Secondly the parallel refereeing factor has not been judged, business satisfaction which may bridge up the liaison between family support and family satisfaction. A third limitation is the lack of awareness to the possible role played by growing cultures, values and ethics to the issues of women entrepreneurship. It is critical for women entrepreneurship research to fully understand the conditions under which the women entrepreneur experience conflict between their roles. There is a need to consider the behavioural research. In addition, further studies to investigate the cross-cultural behaviour studies in different parts of India. The study could also be based on the spiritual aspect on behavioural change in women entrepreneur ship. This spiritual sight would also provide additional insights.

Suggestions For Promoting Women Entrepreneurs In India

Right efforts are required in the improvement of women entrepreneurs and their greater contribution in the entrepreneurial activities. Women entrepreneurs need to be given assurance, freedom, and mobility to come out of their absurdities. The following actions are recommended to authorize the women to grab different opportunities and face challenges in their business.

1. Motivation

There should be a continuous attempt to inspire, encourage, motivate and cooperate women entrepreneurs.

2. Enhance the standards of education

enhance the standards of education of women in general as well making effective provisions for their training, practical experience and personality development programmes, to improvise their overall personality standards.

3. Training

Attempts to establish for them proper training institutes for enhancing their level of work-knowledge, skills, risk-taking abilities, enhancing their capabilities.

Development of women entrepreneurs

bring about a society attitude change, generation of awareness and consciousness on the policy of self-development of women entrepreneurs.

4. Help of NGO's

various NGO's and government organizations to spread information about policies, plans and

strategies on the development of women in the field of industry, trade and commerce.

5. Co operative Association

Forming a cooperative association of women entrepreneurs to mobilize resources and pooling capital funds, in order to help the women in the field of industry, trade and commerce.

6. Seed Capital

Offering seed capital, uplifting schemes, women entrepreneurs fund etc. to encourage them economically.

7. To establish all India forums

To establish all India forums to discuss the problems, grievances, issues, and filing complaints against constraints or shortcomings towards the economic progress path of women entrepreneurs and giving suitable decisions in the favour of women entrepreneurs and taking strict stand against the policies

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